

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FIBER ORIENTATION ANGLE AND STATIC BENDING CHARACTERISTIC OF LAMINATED BAMBOO PLATES

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Keywords: Bamboo-fiber reinforced laminated plates, Material design, Bamboo-fiber orientation angle, Static bending characteristics

ABSTRACT

The static bending characteristics of a single plate and a laminated plate made of bamboo with fiber orientation angles (θ_f) at intervals smaller than those in a previous report were examined experimentally with reference to the elementary beam theory. First, a single plate with an arbitrary orientation (SPAO) was investigated in detail. Laminated plates with arbitrary orientations (LPAOs) were formed by the lamination of SPAO. The rigidity and strength of LPAOs were strongly affected by the fiber orientation angle of the outer SPAO. Compared with the case of aluminum, the equivalent specific rigidity of LPAOs with lamination number $N = 3$ and 4 is small. Thus, the rigidity of LPAOs was high. It is considered that bamboo-fiber-reinforced laminated plates can be used in material design when the desired N , θ_f , and material characteristics are suitable as shown in a table. Moreover, an example of the applications of LPAOs to a pico-Electric Vehicle, which is an ultrasmall personal vehicle for the elderly, is introduced.

1 INTRODUCTION

In order to reduce the environmental load of producing industrial products and recycling, it is important to use natural resources[1]. Bamboo, which is a vegetable fiber material, has strong anisotropy. In Japan, bamboo is used as a laminate lumber for baseball bats, a flooring material, and a framework [2] of a door. Recently, bamboo fiber materials have been studied as door trim and mat materials of a luggage room of a vehicle [3 - 5], and their utilization [6 - 8] has progressed.

In a previous study [9], as the first step toward developing a bamboo-fiber-reinforced laminated material, sawn bamboo sheets [2] were arranged at arbitrary angles of 0° , 45° , and 90° and laminated, and a bamboo-fiber-laminated plate was thus manufactured. The static bending characteristics of laminated plates were examined experimentally with reference to the elementary beam theory. As a result, the bamboo-fiber-laminated plate clarified that fiber reinforcement was possible.

In this study, a detailed evaluation of the static bending characteristics of a bamboo single plate was first performed using a bamboo single plate and then bamboo-fiber-laminated plates with fiber orientation angles at 15° intervals in the range from 0° to 90° . An example of the applications to an ultrasmall one-person electric vehicle (pico-Electric Vehicle: pico-EV) for the elderly was demonstrated.

2 SPECIMEN AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

2.1 Preparation of specimen

The specimen used is swan Moso bamboo [9], and the outline of its manufacturing process is shown below. After cutting down the specimen shown in Fig. 1(a) into strips shown in Fig. 1(b), the strips were laminated with the laminate lumber of a unidirectional fiber. The thin plate that sliced the laminate lumber thinly is marketed as a swan bamboo sheet shown in Fig. 1(c). A single plate with an arbitrary orientation (SPAO) has one swan bamboo plate. Seven types of specimen with a fiber orientation angle θ_f of 0° in the longitudinal direction are shown in Table 1. The SPAO specimens have

a width of $b = 55$ mm and a thickness of $t = 2.10 - 2.41$ mm, as shown in Fig. 2. Laminated plates with arbitrary orientations (LPAOs) were prepared on the basis of the previous θ_f value by antisymmetric lamination with the lamination number $N = 2, 3,$ and 4 for coupling effect control. Polyvinyl-acetate-resin emulsion-type adhesives were used for the adhesion of a plate. The desired adhesion layer thickness was set to $t_b = 0.05$ mm. The plate was dried at a humidity of about 40% at room temperature after press fitting with a vise for 24 h. Several examples of LPAOs are shown in Fig. 3.

2.2 Bending experiment and evaluated term

The span L values of SPAOs and LPAOs are $L = 200$ mm in the case of cantilever bending shown in Fig. 4 and $L = 410$ mm in the case of three-point bending shown in Fig. 5. In order to determine the material characteristics of bamboo, a cantilever bending experiment was performed, as shown in Fig. 4. A static load P was applied to the free end of the specimen, and the bending deflection y was measured. The accuracy was determined to be 0.05 mm using a height gauge. A diagram of the nondimensional bending deflection y_n , which divided y at each point by the maximum bending deflection y_{max} , is shown in Fig. 6. When the distribution of bending deflection approximated with the elementary beam theoretical value, a false longitudinal elastic modulus E^* was obtained using Eq. (1), where L is the span, and I is the second modulus of inertia.

$N=1, \theta_f [^\circ]$	0	15	30	45	60	75	90
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Table 1: Fiber orientation angle of SPAO.

Figure 1: Raw materials of specimen (unidirectional fibers of lamina).

Figure 2: Example of SPAO specimens.

Figure 3: Example of LPAOs specimens.

Figure 4: Experimental setup (Cantilever bending).

Figure 5: Experimental setup (Three-point bending).

The material characteristics generated by the laminated constitution of the lamination number N and fiber orientation angle θ_f were examined. The total plate thickness t of a laminated plate, the section modulus Z , and the specimen mass m_s increased with N . Since bending deflection required the use of as large a measurement value as possible, when N was large, the applied load P and bending moment M became large. Therefore, in order to examine the rigidity of a specimen systematically, the equivalent ratio rigidity R was determined from Eq. (2). Since R was small, the rigidities of the specimens were considered to be high.

The coupling effect of SPAO was determined by cantilever bending using the measured coupling angle α , which is at the free end of the specimen. The breaking stress σ_b was obtained using Eq. (3) in a three-point bending experiment with the mass m applied at the center of the specimen, as shown in Fig. 5. The maximum bending deflection y_{max} was measured using a height gage at the loading point on the opposite site of the specimen. ν_X shown in Eq. (4) is Poisson's ratio in the X-axis of the structural principal axis [10]. The strains ϵ_X and ϵ_Z in the X- and Z- directions, respectively, were measured using strain gages (Kyowa Electronic Instruments Co., Ltd., Japan, Type: KFG-2-120-D16-16) cemented at 20 mm from the fixed end, as shown in Fig. 7.

The number of specimens used in the experiment is five per laminated constitution, and the results shown are average values.

3 MATERIAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SPAO

The coupling effects shown in Fig. 8 are as follows: α is small at $\theta_f = 0^\circ$ and 90° , and most SPAOs do not rotate. α is maximum at $\theta_f = 45^\circ$, and an almost symmetrical tendency is observed for the distribution of α bordering at $\theta_f = 45^\circ$. From $\theta_f = 0^\circ$, ν_X , which is Poisson's ratio in the X-axis of the structural principal axis shown in Fig. 9 by the symbol \bigcirc , decreased when θ_f is increased to 90° . $\nu_X = 0.22 - 0.08$ is smaller than the range 0.335 - 0.617 of *Quercus crispula* that inhabits a cold district, 0.330 - 0.646 of the Japanese elm, 0.283 - 0.671 [11] of a beech, and 0.245 [12] of glass, or 0.280 - 0.300 of steel. Therefore, if the fiber orientation is inclined toward the width direction of SPAO, the brittleness of the material will increase.

$$E^* = \frac{PL^3}{3y_{max}I} \quad (1)$$

$$R = \frac{y_{max}}{m_s MI} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_b = \frac{M}{Z} \quad (3)$$

$$\nu_X = -\frac{\epsilon_X}{\epsilon_Z} \quad (4)$$

Figure 6: Non-dimensional bending deflection of SPAO (Cantilever bending, $\theta_f = 30^\circ$)

Figure 7: Strain measurement of SPAO (Cantilever bending)

The R shown in Fig. 9 by the symbol \triangle is smallest at $\theta_f = 0^\circ$, and once R takes a large value at $\theta_f = 45^\circ$, it decreases and becomes maximum at $\theta_f = 90^\circ$. Therefore, the bending rigidity of SPAO is largest at $\theta_f = 0^\circ$.

The E^* shown in Fig. 10 by the symbol \circ decreases in the θ_f range from 0° to 30° . The E^* in the θ_f range from 45° to 90° , which is about 1/3 to 1/4 that in the θ_f range from $\theta_f = 0^\circ$ to 30° , is small. The E^* in the range from $\theta_f = 45^\circ$ to 90° shows a convex tendency. Generally, E^* was distributed over the range of 6.1GPa - 1.3GPa. A monotonic decrease in σ_b shown in Fig. 10 by the symbol \triangle occurs in the first half from $\theta_f = 0^\circ$ to 30° . σ_b falls rapidly and shows a weak convex tendency in the second half of $\theta_f = 45^\circ$. The σ_b of this range, which is 1/2 to 1/4 in the first half of θ_f , is small. Generally, σ_b is distributed over the σ_b range of 66.2 MPa to 15.8 MPa.

A fractured specimen is shown in Fig. 11. Near the span center, which is the loading point, the specimen is fractured in the fibrous direction except for $\theta_f = 0^\circ$. For the SPAO, at $\theta_f = 45^\circ$, most of the E^* and ν_x values around the structure principal axis, and R and σ_b , which were obtained in the experimental range considered, indicate the turning point of a tendency.

Figure 8: Coupling angle of SPAO (Cantilever bending)

Figure 9: Poisson's ratio and equivalent specific rigidity of SPAO.

Figure 10: False elastic modulus and breaking stress of SPAO.

4 MATERIAL CHARACTERISTICS OF LPAOs

In order to compare with the rigidity of the bamboo-fiber-reinforced LPAOs, the experimental result [9] of the aluminum material, which is light and isotropic, was used. Unlike the case of SPAO, the indicator of the laminated constitution of LPAOs omits that of the angle [$^{\circ}$]; for example, at $N = 2$, the indicator is described as $\theta_f = (45/-45)$ and so forth as $\theta_f =$ (upper layer / lower layer).

The laminated constitution for evaluating rigidity using E^* and R was considered, as shown in Table 2, from the characteristics of SPAO. That is, (1) at $N = 2$ by antisymmetric lamination, the characteristic thickness of SPAO is doubled. (2) In the case of plate bending, the bending stress in the central portion is close to zero. In the case of SPAO at $N = 1$, $\theta_f = 45^{\circ}$ shows the turning point of a tendency. Then, for $N = 3$, $\theta_f = 0^{\circ}$, 45° , and 90° are chosen as the central portions of plate thickness, and both outer sides of SPAO of the θ_f value shown in Table 1 are laminated. (3) For $N = 4$, the fiber orientation in the central portion of plate thickness is the same as that for $N = 2$. Moreover, at both outer sides of SPAO, $\theta_f = 0^{\circ}$ with the highest E^* value is obtained. $\theta_f = 0^{\circ}$ and 45° , which is the turning point of a tendency, and $\theta_f = -45^{\circ}$ of antisymmetric are also obtained.

The present author decided to examine the characteristics of SPAO by considering the laminated constitutions of the thickness central portion and outer sides of the laminated plate.

4.1 False longitudinal elastic modulus

E^* is shown by the symbol \bigcirc in Fig. 12. If it is set to $\theta_f = (15/-15)$ and $(30/-30)$ from $\theta_f = (0/0)$ at $N = 2$, E^* will fall rapidly. E^* of $\theta_f = (30/-30)$ is about 44% of that of $\theta_f = (0/0)$, and this value is about 63% of that of $\theta_f = 30^{\circ}$ at $N = 1$. The E^* of $\theta_f = (45/-45)$ set to $(60/-60)$ and $(75/-75)$, which is about 10% to 25% of that of $\theta_f = (30/-30)$, is low. The E^* of $\theta_f = (90/-90)$ is about 50% each of $\theta_f = (45/-45)$,

Figure 11: Breaking specimens of SPAO (Three-point bending).

$N=2$	$N=3$			$N=4$	
$(\theta_f/-\theta_f)$	$(\theta_f/0/-\theta_f)$	$(\theta_f/45/-\theta_f)$	$(\theta_f/90/-\theta_f)$	$(0/\theta_f/-\theta_f/0)$	$(45/\theta_f/-\theta_f/-45)$
(0/0)	(0/0/0)	(0/45/0)	(0/90/0)	(0/0/0/0)	(45/0/0/-45)
(15/-15)	(15/0/-15)	(15/45/-15)	(15/90/-15)	(0/15/-15/0)	(45/15/-15/-45)
(30/-30)	(30/0/-30)	(30/45/-30)	(30/90/-30)	(0/30/-30/0)	(45/30/-30/-45)
(45/-45)	(45/0/-45)	(45/45/-45)	(45/90/-45)	(0/45/-45/0)	(45/45/-45/-45)
(60/-60)	(60/0/-60)	(60/45/-60)	(60/90/-60)	(0/60/-60/0)	(45/60/-60/-45)
(75/-75)	(75/0/-75)	(75/45/-75)	(75/90/-75)	(0/75/-75/0)	(45/75/-75/-45)
(90/-90)	(90/0/-90)	(90/45/-90)	(90/90/-90)	(0/90/-90/0)	(45/90/-90/-45)

Table 2: Lamination constitution of LPAOs (for E^* and R).

(60/-60), and (75/-75). Generally, E^* distributes over the range of 6.9 GPa - 1.2 GPa. A value lower than that of SPAO of $N=1$ may be shown, and the reason is under examination now.

At $N=3$, the expression of the laminated constitution is changed with $(\theta_f/0/-\theta_f)$, $(\theta_f/45/-\theta_f)$, and $(\theta_f/90/-\theta_f)$. When $(\theta_f/0/-\theta_f)$ is considered a sample representation, the E^* in the first half of (0/0/0) to (15/0/-15) and (30/0/-30) decreases monotonically. On the other hand, the E^* in the second half of $\theta_f=(45/0/-45)$ to (60/0/-60), (75/0/-75), and (90/0/-90) has a distribution with a weak convex tendency similarly to that of $\theta_f=45^\circ$ to 90° for SPAO. Generally, the E^* itself distributes between 8.3 GPa to 5.8 GPa. The E^* values in the first half of $\theta_f=(30/0/-30)$ and in the second half after (45/0/-45) are practically equal to those in the case of SPAO. The distribution tendency of E^* and the E^* itself relative to the laminated constitution are also the same in $(\theta_f/45/-\theta_f)$ and $(\theta_f/90/-\theta_f)$.

Therefore, in this experiment, the E^* of $N=3$ is not based on the θ_f obtained at the center of SPAO, but it is clearly affected by the θ_f of SPAO obtained on the surface outside a laminated plate. Although the E^* values of $(0/\theta_f/-\theta_f/0)$ and $N=2$ show similar tendencies, the E^* itself increases greatly and distributes in the range of 9.0 GPa - 5.6 GPa. In the case of $(45/\theta_f/-\theta_f/45)$, even if the θ_f of the central portion of a plate changes, E^* distributes in an almost fixed range of 2.7 GPa - 2.0 GPa, and is as small as 1/3 that in the case of $(0/\theta_f/-\theta_f/0)$, which is observed on both outer sides of SPAO of $\theta_f=0^\circ$.

4.2 Equivalent specific rigidity

R is shown in Fig. 12 by the symbol \square . At $N=2$, R is large with an increase in θ_f , as observed in SPAO. At $N=3$ and 4, R is not based on the laminated constitution, is almost constant, and is smaller than that of the aluminum material. Therefore, the laminated constitution range is covered and fiber reinforcement is possible.

4.3 Breaking stress

The laminated constitution for evaluating σ_b shown in Table 3 is based on the σ_b of SPAO. (1) At $N=2$, the laminated constitution is the same as that for evaluating rigidity. (2) In SPAO, the first half from $\theta_f=0^\circ$ to 30° tends to differ from that of the second half after $\theta_f=45^\circ$. Therefore, $\theta_f=0^\circ, 45^\circ$, and 90° are chosen and set to both outer sides of SPAO at $N=3$. On the basis of these results, SPAO of θ_f shown in Table 1 is considered laminated at its thickness central portion. (3) At $N=4$, the laminated constitution of the central portion of the plate thickness is made to be the same as that at $N=2$, and $\theta_f=45^\circ$ and 90° with a small σ_b of SPAO are obtained on both outer sides of the laminated plate.

Although the maximum load $P_{max}=412$ N obtained in this laboratory was applied to the specimen of $\theta_f=(0/0/0/0)$ and $(0/90/90/0)$, the signs of fracture were not seen. Therefore, this specimen was excluded from the experiment. At the beginning, it is considered that the laminated constitution is the

Figure 12: False elastic modulus and equivalent specific rigidity of LPAOs.

same as that in Table 2. However, the present author decided to examine the characteristic laminated constitution by considering the σ_b of SPAO.

The obtained σ_b values are shown in Fig. 13. At $N = 2$, a tendency that is extremely similar to that obtained in SPAO is shown in Fig. 9, and σ_b distributes over the range of 60.8 MPa - 54.3 MPa from $\theta_f = 0^\circ - 30^\circ$ and over that of 30.1 MPa - 12.4 MPa after $\theta_f = 45^\circ$. These values are smaller by about 8% - 22% than those of SPAO. When the laminated plate thickness became twice in SPAO, it increased twice as much as the cross-sectional coefficient, and predicted that σ_b also increased simply, but the result became smaller than that of SPAO. The reason for this is under examination now. $N = 3$ is obtained at $(0/-\theta_f/0)$. Even if the θ_f of the central portion of SPAO changes, the difference in σ_b is negligible. The value distributes over the range of about 90.8 MPa - 79.5 MPa and the strength of SPAO of $\theta_f = 0^\circ$ is considered to increase though lamination. The σ_b values of $(45/\theta_f/-45)$ and $(90/\theta_f/-90)$ distribute in the ranges of 25.4 MPa - 18.4 MPa and 22.4MPa - 18.1MPa, respectively. These values are about 1/4 of that of $(0/-\theta_f/0)$ and fall sharply. The σ_b values of $\theta_f = 45^\circ$ and 90° in SPAO are considered to fall greatly to 42% and 61% of that of $\theta_f = 0^\circ$, respectively. The characteristic σ_b at $N= 4$ is shown in Fig. 13. The σ_b values of $(45/\theta_f/-\theta_f/-45)$ and $(90/\theta_f/-\theta_f/-90)$ distribute in the ranges of 27.2 MPa - 20.2 MPa and 24.1 MPa - 18.5 MPa, respectively. There is no quite difference in these values in the cases of $(45/\theta_f/-45)$ and $(90/\theta_f/-90)$. Therefore, if weight reduction and strength improvement are considered in this experiment, the laminated constitution of $(0/-\theta_f/0)$ is advantageous.

Generally, it turned out that the σ_b of a bamboo-fiber-laminated plate is greatly governed by that of SPAO on both the outer sides of the laminated plate. This is the same as that in the case of fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) materials [10].

N=2	N=3			N=4	
$(\theta_f/-\theta_f)$	$(0/\theta_f/0)$	$(45/\theta_f/-45)$	$(90/\theta_f/-90)$	$(45/\theta_f/-\theta_f/-45)$	$(90/\theta_f/-\theta_f/-90)$
$(0/0)$	$(0/0/0)$	$(45/0/-45)$	$(90/0/-90)$	$(45/0/0/-45)$	$(90/0/0/-90)$
$(15/-15)$	$(0/15/0)$	$(45/15/-45)$	$(90/15/-90)$	$(45/15/-15/-45)$	$(90/15/-15/-90)$
$(30/-30)$	$(0/30/0)$	$(45/30/-45)$	$(90/30/-90)$	$(45/30/-30/-45)$	$(90/30/-30/-90)$
$(45/-45)$	$(0/45/0)$	$(45/45/-45)$	$(90/45/-90)$	$(45/45/-45/-45)$	$(90/45/-45/-90)$
$(60/-60)$	$(0/60/0)$	$(45/60/-45)$	$(90/60/-90)$	$(45/60/-60/-45)$	$(90/60/-60/-90)$
$(75/-75)$	$(0/75/0)$	$(45/75/-45)$	$(90/75/-90)$	$(45/75/-75/-45)$	$(90/75/-75/-90)$
$(90/-90)$	$(0/90/0)$	$(45/90/-45)$	$(90/90/-90)$	$(45/90/-90/-45)$	$(90/90/-90/-90)$

Table 3: Lamination constitution of LPAOs (for σ_b).

Figure 13: Breaking stress of LPAOs

The M - y diagram obtained from the three-point bending experiment is shown in Fig. 14. The maximum break stress was determined to be $\sigma_{b, max} = 103.7$ MPa, and the minimum value was $\sigma_{b, min} = 34.7$ MPa. According to Figs. 15 (a) - (c), a fractured specimen was obtained by a destructive mechanism induced by the lamination constitution. The $\theta_f = (0/0/0)$ case in Fig. 15 (a) shows a broken tensile specimen. Moreover, the $\theta_f = (45/0/-45)$ case in Fig. 15 (b) shows the same tendency as that observed in Fig. 15 (a). The outer surface of the tensile specimen broke along the fiber direction at an angle of 45° . According to the $\theta_f = (90/0/90)$ case in Fig. 15 (c), the outer surface of the $\theta_f = 90^\circ$ layer cracked, and the fibers at the center of the $\theta_f = 0^\circ$ layer broke. In any case, destruction between the layers was not observed; thus, it is considered that the adhesion strength of the manufactured laminated plate is high.

The cost in the case of having a bending rigidity equivalent to that of LPAOs of $N=4$ was compared with aluminum and steel. Results indicate that LPAOs are about 55% and 77% cheaper than the aluminum and steel materials, respectively.

5 BAMABOO LPAOs APPLIED TO DEVELOPMENT OF ULTRALIGHT AND SMALL ELECTRIC VEHICLE : pico-EV

To confirm this result, bamboo LPAOs were applied as the structural member of an ultralight and small electric vehicle (pico-EV), which was designed and developed in our previous study [13]. As shown in Fig. 16, the design and development of pico-EV began in 2009, and our pico-EV was entered into all pico-EV Eco-Challenge competitions [14, 15].

The concept of pico-EV is as follows. (1) Six AA rechargeable dry cell batteries are used in accordance with the regulations of a pico-EV Eco-Challenge competition, as sponsored by the Japan Society of Mechanical Engineers (JSME). (2) The vehicle is elderly friendly and can travel at a super low speed; it is ultrasmall, light, and affordable, and has low maintenance and management costs. (3) It can be carried into an airplane.

pico-EV2014, which is the newest developed vehicle, is shown in Figs. 17 and 18. It has two rear wheels as the driving wheels, and a friction drive of the perimeter of a wheel with each motor axis, and realizes a minimum turning radius of 0.5 m using the difference in the rotational velocity of each wheel. Its body weight is 10.5 kg, and its running speed is 1.2 km/h. The design concept using bamboo

Figure 14: Bending moment and deflection of LPAOs (Three-point bending).

Figure 15: Broken specimens of LPAOs (Three-point bending).

fiber material was evaluated, in the pico-EV2014 Eco-Challenge competition [16] and won the eco-challenge prize. By checking for damage to the structural member of pico-EV after running in a competition, breakage was not observed, and thus the vehicle is practically useful.

Figure 16: pico-EV histories.

Figure 17: pico-EV2014.

Figure 18: Assembling and decomposition of pico-EV2014.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The static bending characteristics of a bamboo single plate and bamboo-fiber laminated plates were examined experimentally. The static bending characteristics of the laminated plates manufactured using the experimental results were examined from the viewpoint of material design. An ultrasmall electric vehicle was designed using the acquired material characteristics. The results are as follows.

- (1) Several types of specimen were prepared according to the bamboo fiber orientation angle in the range from 0° to 90° at 15° intervals from $\theta_f = 0^\circ$, and a static bending experiment was conducted for numbers of laminations of $N = 1, 2, 3,$ and 4 . From the obtained experimental results, the characteristics of such specimens were determined and are shown in a table. It is considered that a static material design is possible on the basis of these characteristics.
- (2) The rigidity and strength of a bamboo-fiber-laminated plate are greatly affected by the characteristics of single plates arranged on both the outer sides of the laminated plate.
- (3) When weight reduction and strength improvement are considered in this experiment, $(0/-\theta_f/0)$ of $N = 3$ lamination is advantageous.
- (4) The Poisson's ratio of bamboo is smaller than those of steel, glass, and wood species that inhabit a cold district.
- (5) In this laminated constitution, in any case, the destruction between the layers was not observed. Thus, it is considered that the adhesion strength of the manufactured laminated plate is high.
- (6) Breakage of the component was not observed when a bamboo-fiber-reinforced laminated plate developed in this study was applied as the structural member of a one-person pico-EV for the elderly. Therefore, our pico-EV is practically useful.

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